

DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT FEEDING TECHNIQUES WITH MICRO-STRIP PATCH ANTENNA

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Abstract

The paper represents comparison of different feeding techniques for micro-strip antenna while considering parameters such as bandwidth, antenna gain, return loss, VSWR (Voltage Standing Wave ratio) and antenna directivity. The result is generated from micro strip planar antenna having a substrate Retardant 4 (FR-4) with dielectric constant of 4.4 thicknesses of 1.6mm and targeted S-band resonant frequency 3.5 GHz for performance analysis. From the simulation results it is retrieved that aperture feed gives better gain performance while microstrip feed generates better return loss compare to other feed techniques.

Introduction

The various antenna in the range of Super High Frequency (3GHz-30GHz) for application Satellite Links, Wireless Communication, but as demand increases of microstrip antenna due to its small size, planer structure and easy of fabrication. Microstrip patch antenna are made up of two conducting layer and one dielectric substrate.

The various antennas like Rectangular horn, log-periodic, parabolic in the range of Super High Frequency (3GHz-30GHz) are used in the applications of Satellite links, Wireless Communication [1-3]. However, they are much more bulky in size so the demand for light weight antenna increases [4]. Moreover, rectangular waveguide components are difficult to manufacture and integrate with planar circuitry due to their 3D geometry [5]. Therefore, planar antenna especially microstrip antenna is preferred due to its small size, and easy of fabrication using standard PCB (Printed Circuit Board) fabrication technique [6]. Microstrip patch antenna is made up of two conducting layer and one dielectric substrate [7]. It provides advantage of low profile, light weight, low cost and high efficiency. These advantages will help to allow use of antenna in various applications [8]. in the microstrip antenna, radiation take place due to fringing effect from patch edge to ground for that patch always etched in substrate, and shape of patch may be circular, rectangle or triangle [1]. For better performance of rectangle patch, it is generally consider substrate is made up of high dielectric. However, high die

lectric substrate generates more losses. On the other side, low dielectric substrate which provides better radiation with large bandwidth. For practical application, either compact structure or higher dielectric constant has to select to get the compact design or better performance.

Another important parameter in planar structure is to choose feed techniques. There are various feed techniques are available like, (i) Microstrip (ii) Cut through (iii) Coaxial (iv) Aperture feed (v) Proximity feed [9]. Depending on the requirement and integrate with different components feeding techniques have been selected. From above, we have concentrated the design of all the feed techniques to the S band antenna (taken example to application prove) and summarize the performance in terms of gain and return loss into this paper.

Selection of Dielectric Substrate: For the positive performance and to moderate the size of antenna select a thin dielectric substrate which has low dielectric constant and loss tangent for better bandwidth, gain, efficiency and low power losses. Here the substrate used is FR4 which has dielectric constant of permittivity 4.4, height of the substrate is 1.58 and the operating frequency of the microstrip antenna is 3.5GHz [11].

- Length: $0.33 \lambda_0 < l < 0.5 \lambda_0$
- Height: $0.003 \lambda_0 < h < 0.05 \lambda_0$
- Thickness(t): $t < \lambda_0$
- Dielectric Concentration (ϵ_r): $2.2 \lambda_0 < \epsilon_r < 12 \lambda_0$

Microstrip patch antenna can be fed by a different method [3]. Basically feeding technique can be divided in two parts micro strip line. In contact feed radiating power directly feed to the patch by contacting element for non-contacting feed technique, electromagnetic field couple done to transfer power [2].

Figure 1 overview of feeding techniques

Mathematics

The radiation pattern, bandwidth, gain and directivity can depends on dielectric constant, height of dielectric, feed line length, aperture width. Calculation of parameters is shown below. Selection of these parameters required properly because this affects overall response of antenna [10].

Figure 2 Basic microstrip structure

Calculation for all feeding techniques

- The Width Of Patch

$$W = \frac{c}{2f \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

- The Effective Constant Can Be Obtained By

$$\epsilon_{\text{reff}} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{w} \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Where ϵ_{reff} = effective dielectric constant,

ϵ_r = dielectric constant of substrate,

H = height of dielectric substrate,

W = width of patch

- Length Of Patch

$$L = \frac{\lambda_0}{2} + 2\Delta L \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Where } \Delta L = 0.412h \frac{(\epsilon_{\text{reff}} + 0.3) \left(\frac{w}{h} + 0.264 \right)}{(\epsilon_{\text{reff}} - 0.258) \left(\frac{w}{h} + 0.8 \right)} \quad (4)$$

- Ground Dimension

$$L_g = 6h + L, W_g = 6h + W \quad (5)$$

Here, as we select conducting material Retardant 4 (FR-4) and design antenna for frequency 3.5GHz, for this frequency we achieve λ_0 85.71mm, operating mode TE₁₀ and from above equation we derived patch dimensions 19.97mm X 26.06mm and ground plane dimension 29.57mm X 35.66mm. The dimension of the patch along

with its length has been extended by a distance ΔL due to the fringing field which is a function of effective dielectric constant.

Table 1 Dimensions of patch and ground.

Parameter	Dimensions
Patch width	26.06mm
Patch length	19.97mm
Dielectric constant	4.4
Feed width	0.5mm
Ground width	35.66mm
Ground length	29.57mm

A. MICRO STRIP FEED

In simple microstrip feeding structure feed line is connected to the center of edge and due to this it's provide planar construction. Here, we have considered the design of antenna for 3.5GHZ frequency which is shown in figure 3. As shown in figure 4, it generates return loss of -35.5dB. Also, it gives the gain of 2.1dB which is shown in figure 5 and figure 6 shows the E field radiation pattern. It also gives the VSWR 1.67. Achieved bandwidth = $f_2 - f_1 = 150\text{MHz}$.

Figure 3 Microstrip feed

Figure 4 Return loss for microstrip feed

Figure 5 Gain plot for micro strip antenna

Figure 6 Radiation pattern plot

ii) CUT THROUGH FEED

By applying cut in micro strip feed line as shown in figure 7, we are matching input impedance with our antenna without design of any external circuit. Simulated results are shown below as we design antenna for 3.5GHz frequency and we observed the response of return loss of -20.5dB shown in figure 8, gain of 1dB shown in figure 9, and radiation pattern shown in figure 10. Moreover, it gives VSWR of 1.07. Drawback of cut through feed microstrip patch antenna is cross polarization.

Figure 7 Cut through feed

Figure 9 Gain plot for cut through patch antenna

Figure 8 Return loss for cut through feed

Figure 10 Radiation pattern for cut through feed antenna

B. COAXIAL FEED

In the coaxial feed antenna, feeding is applied by coaxial wire which provides lower bandwidth because it provide direct connecting ground to patch. The coax feed microstrip antenna is shown in figure 11. Simulated parameters for antenna by feeding coaxial line at 3.5GHz are return loss -37dB shown in figure 12, gain about 1dB shown in figure 13 and its radiation pattern shown in figure 14. Also it gives VSWR of 1.24, Achieved bandwidth = $f_2 - f_1 = 180\text{MHz}$.

Figure 11 Coaxial feed microstrip antenna

Figure 12 Return loss for coaxial feed

Figure 13 Gain plot for coaxial feed antenna

Figure 14 Radiation pattern for coaxial feed antenna

C. APERTURE FEED PATCH ANTENNA

In aperture feed patch antenna, ground plane is placed between patch and feeding line, radiation coupling can be possible due to slot in dielectric substrate. Position of coupling is nearly at center which provide low cross polarization which is shown in figure 15. It's also possible to control amount of power transfer by taking care of location and size of aperture. Figure 16 shows the return loss of aperture feed patch antenna which is more than -17.50dB. Also the gain of this type of feed technique 4.4 dB which is shown in figure 17 and its radiation pattern is plotted in figure 18. Achieved band width = $f_2 - f_1 = 190\text{MHz}$.

Figure 15 Aperture Feed antenna design

Figure 16 Return Loss for Aperture antenna

Figure 17 Gain plot for aperture antenna

Figure 18 Radiation pattern plot

D. PROXIMITY FEED PATCH ANTENNA

In the proximity feed patch design, basic architecture is feed line is placed between the layers of dielectric material. Impedance matching can be achieved by choosing proper width and length of feed line. Return loss is show in figure 20 which is more than -20dB and figure 21 shows the gain is 5.23dB. Radiation Pattern of this antenna by using this technique is shown in figure 22. Drawback is overall height of antenna is higher but at same time this provides wider bandwidth. Achieved band width= $f_2 - f_1 = 470\text{MHz}$.

Figure 19 Proximity antenna design

Figure 20 Return loss for proximity patch antenna

Figure 21 Gain plot for proximity antenna

Figure 22 Radiation pattern for proximity antenna

Comparison

Table 2 observed parameter of all the feeding technique

Feeding Technique	Simple	Coaxial	Cut Through	Proximity	Aperture
Band-width	290MHz	180MHz	150MHz	470MHz	190MHz
Gain	3dB	1dB	1dB	5.239dB	4dB
VSWR	1.27	1.03	1.2	1.43	1.24
Return loss	-19.5	-37.50	-20.5	-15	-20.75

Appendix

- SIW...substrate integrated waveguide
- f_rResonant frequency
- ϵ_rdielectric constant
- ϵ_{reff} ...Effective dielectric constant
- c Velocity of Electromagnetic wave, 3×10^{11} mm/s
- fOperating frequency in GHz

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Conclusion

As table 2 shows comparisons of all five feeding methods, as there are different aspects that are involved in the design of the antenna. We observed simple inset feed, coaxial feed provide good efficiency at same time lower bandwidth, from the Figure 23 proximity inset feed technique provide wider bandwidth depends on requirement we can say that there are many aspects that we have to take in consideration and select inset feed method according to that.

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